

MEDICAL SCIENCES

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TREATMENT OF PERIODONTITIS WITH ENZYMO-THERAPY

Abstract

When the inflammation spreads to the deep parts of the periodontium, the vascular system of the periodontium and the periodontal ligament become the primary objects of damage. A sharp increase in vascular wall permeability leads to a violation of the damper function of the periodontium [2].

Key words: *periodontal inflammation, enzyme therapy, polyenzyme preparations*

The large number of existing methods for treating periodontitis reflects the efforts of researchers and clinicians to impact various links of the pathogenetic mechanism of the pathological process. However, the existing treatment protocols and technologies do not always achieve the desired result and full rehabilitation of patients [3]. Systemic enzymotherapy is a therapeutic method using a specially formulated mixture of hydrolytic enzymes of plant and animal origin and rutin, which have a cooperative effect on key physiological and pathophysiological processes [4]. The polyenzyme preparations Wobenzym and Phlogenzym are the most widely used in medical practice [1]. These preparations contain animal and plant proteases that complement each other in their specificity regarding the substrates of inflammation. The polyenzyme preparations contain trypsin, chymotrypsin, amylase, lipase, and pancreatin, derived from animal pancreases, as well as papain and bromelain, extracted from the plants *Carica papaya* and *Ananas comusus*, respectively. Thanks to the biochemical properties of the components, each one has a broad range of effects on various stages of the inflammatory process.

Objective: To study the effect of systemic enzymotherapy on the course of the inflammatory process in the periodontium.

Materials and methods: The study observed 168 patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases of varying severity, aged from 20 to 73 years, including 66 (39.29%) men and 102 (69.71%) women. The duration of the disease ranged from 6 months to 30 years. Chronic generalized periodontitis of mild severity (CGPML) was diagnosed in 75 (44.64%) patients, and chronic generalized periodontitis of moderate severity (CGPMS) was diagnosed in 93 (55.36%) patients. All patients were divided into 3 main groups and 2 comparison groups. The main groups included 34 patients with mild chronic generalized periodontitis (Group 1) and 53 with moderate chronic generalized periodontitis (Groups 2 and 3). The comparison groups consisted of

41 patients with CGPML (Group A) and 40 with CGPMS (Group B). Clinical examination included a survey, inspection, probing, evaluation of tooth mobility, and the condition of the periodontal tissues before treatment, after oral cavity sanitation, and at subsequent visits following complex periodontitis treatment. The Fedorov-Vodkina hygiene index was used to assess the oral hygiene status. The PMA index (papillary-marginal-alveolar) was used to evaluate the condition of the periodontium. The CPITN index (WHO periodontal treatment need index) was used to assess the need for various types of therapeutic and preventive care for periodontal diseases. The comparison groups A and B underwent treatment according to the traditional scheme, commonly accepted in most periodontology departments of dental institutions, while patients in the main groups were treated using a method developed by the authors, with the use of Wobenzym.

For complex restorative therapy, 3 main groups were selected, with patients distributed relatively evenly based on the severity of the disease and the antibacterial medication used. In Group 1, Metrogyl Denta was used in combination with Wobenzym (34 patients), in Group 2, Lincomycin hydrochloride with Wobenzym (29 patients), and in Group 3, Sofradex with Wobenzym (24 patients). Additionally, all patients were prescribed general treatment (vitamin therapy: Ascorutin, Oligovit, or Unicap – T). The obtained results were processed using methods of variation statistics with the Student's t-test. Calculations were performed on a personal computer using Microsoft Excel 2003 statistical analysis software for Windows XP.

Results and Discussion: A comprehensive analysis confirmed positive treatment dynamics in patients in all groups, but the best results were achieved in the main groups where medicinal compositions based on Wobenzym were used in combination with antibacterial therapy. The use of medicinal compositions with Wobenzym in patients of Group 1 was conducted over 5-6 sessions. By the 2nd-3rd visit (1-3 days), patients

reported improvement in their periodontal condition. Bad breath disappeared, itching and burning in the gums ceased, and there was a reduction in gum bleeding and pain. Objective examination revealed no hyperemia, cyanosis, or edema, and reduced bleeding of the gum tissue in all patients of this group. After the course of treatment (7-14 days), the periodontal assessment index values changed and corresponded to normal mean values: PI – 0.97 ± 0.06 ; PMA – $2.14 \pm 0.26\%$; CPITN – 0.31 ± 0.03 . Shiller-Pisarev test was negative in 32 ($94.12 \pm 4.0\%$) patients. According to the index evaluation, the effectiveness of the traditional method was at a lower level. In Group A, the duration of the treatment course until the complete disappearance of clinical signs of inflammation was 7-8 visits. By the 3rd-4th visit (3-7 days), patients reported improvement in their periodontal condition. Bad breath disappeared, itching and burning in the gums ceased, and there was a reduction in gum bleeding and pain. Objective examination showed a significant decrease in inflammatory phenomena, reduction in hyperemia, bleeding, and edema of the gum papilla mucosa in all patients of this group. This is evidenced by the following index assessment values of the periodontal and oral hygiene condition: PI – 1.48 ± 0.08 , PMA – $10.37 \pm 1.32\%$, CPITN – 1.47 ± 0.04 . Shiller-Pisarev tests were negative in $80.49 \pm 6.2\%$ of patients. The use of the Wobenzym medicinal composition in patients of Groups 2 and 3 was conducted in 6-8 sessions. Already by the 2nd-3rd visit (1-3 days), patients reported improvement in their periodontal condition. There was no bad breath, itching or burning in the gums ceased, and there was a reduction in gum bleeding and pain. Decrease in inflammation was observed on the 3rd-7th day (edema disappeared, the gums became pale pink and did not bleed). The index values for periodontal tissue condition and oral hygiene in Group 2 decreased significantly, and were as follows: PI – 1.23 ± 0.07 , PMA – $2.68 \pm 0.22\%$, CPITN – 0.40 ± 0.13 . Shiller-Pisarev tests were negative in $93.10 \pm 4.7\%$ of patients. In Group 3, the index values also decreased and were normal: PI – 1.27 ± 0.03 , PMA – $2.49 \pm 0.19\%$, CPITN – 0.39 ± 0.16 . Shiller-Pisarev tests were negative in $91.67 \pm 5.6\%$ of patients. In Group B, the index values were higher than those in Groups 2 and 3: PI – 1.98 ± 0.08 , PMA – $13.41 \pm 2.04\%$, CPITN – 1.69 ± 0.03 . Shiller-Pisarev tests were negative in $77.50 \pm 6.6\%$ of patients. A month after therapy, improvement in the periodontal tissue condition, up to complete resolution of the inflammatory process, was observed in all patients of Group 1. They reported no complaints. Objective examination showed restoration of the gum color to pale pink, gum papillae to proper shape, with the formation of a firm cuff along the line of the tooth-gum attachment. The index values of periodontal tissue condition and oral hygiene decreased significantly and were as follows: PI – 0.77 ± 0.2 , PMA – $1.88 \pm 0.12\%$, CPITN – 0.31 ± 0.03 . Shiller-Pisarev test was negative. In comparison, 36 ($87.80 \pm 5.1\%$) patients

in Group A showed normalization of periodontal tissue condition. The index values for periodontal tissue condition and oral hygiene changed as follows: PI – 1.40 ± 0.09 , PMA – $10.05 \pm 0.95\%$, CPITN – 1.49 ± 0.02 . Shiller-Pisarev test was negative in $87.80 \pm 5.1\%$ of patients. One month after treatment, no clinical signs of inflammation were found in all patients of Group 2. Patients reported no complaints, and the mucous membrane of the gums had a normal color, and the contour of the gum margin was fully restored. Clinically, edema of the gum mucosa decreased, and the contour of the gum margin partially recovered. Observations of the pathological process in the periodontium showed that after comprehensive treatment, significant improvement in the clinical situation was noted in patients with moderate periodontitis. There was no hyperemia or edema of the interdental gum papillae, and the gum edge became firm and adhered to the tooth necks. Positive dynamics in the index values of periodontal tissue condition and oral hygiene were noted: PI – 0.99 ± 0.04 , PMA – $2.46 \pm 0.04\%$, CPITN – 0.41 ± 0.13 . All patients in Group 3, one month after treatment, showed no clinical signs of inflammation. Patients reported no complaints, and the mucous membrane of the gums had normal color. Clinically, gum mucosa edema and inflammation disappeared. Normalization of periodontal tissue and oral hygiene occurred, and the values of indices were PI – 1.27 ± 0.08 , PMA – $2.43 \pm 0.11\%$, CPITN – 0.43 ± 0.07 .

Conclusion: The use of systemic enzymotherapy with Wobenzym preparation in the complex therapy of patients with chronic generalized periodontitis leads to significant improvement in the clinical condition of the periodontium. It allows for faster and more efficient resolution of the inflammatory process, improving periodontal and oral hygiene index values.

References

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4. Kenbaev V.O., Dyusupov K.B. Comprehensive Treatment of Diffuse Phlegmons of the Neck // Probl. Stomatol. – 2003. – No. 4 (22). Summary: The inclusion of the proposed drug compositions based on the Wobenzym drug and antibacterial agents in the comprehensive treatment contributes to the increased clinical effectiveness of restorative therapy, stabilization of the process, and prolonged remission.